

IPBES AR BBA Chapter 2 – Snowballing literature search for literature on business dependencies on biodiversity (R6)

Template to group the studies under different ecosystem services dependencies categories and the sectors that received the benefits. Including the name of the category (category), its description (description) and the possible answer categories (answer categories).

Information category	Description	Answer categories
ID	Unique ID given to each reference	--
Ecosystem_services	Ecosystem services studied.	As listed in R3
Units	Units of the value of the magnitude.	Open answer
Categories	Grouping units within four main categories that assess ecosystem services dependencies.	<p>Select one category of the following list:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Economic valuation: monetary units (R5). • Productivity: values that were important for yield production, for instance, yield or water needed to produce a product (R5). • Quality: values that reflected how a product was enhanced due to the ecosystem services, for instance, increase shelf life for a crop (R5). • Risk: The risk of losing or negatively impacting ecosystem services could affect the sector itself. For instance, natural disasters and water use from water-scarce regions pose significant threats (R5).
Short_description	A description of the units and their intended use (e.g., describe how vulnerable a business is when losing pollinators).	Open answer
Comment	Any additional comment that the researcher wanted to provide.	Open answer
Sector_benefitted	Write the sector that received the benefits from ecosystem services.	Open answer

If_other_category	If other dependency category was identified the researcher had the opportunity to describe it.	Open answer
Reviewer	Name of the reviewer that was a lead author (anonymized).	Open answer